

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE STUDENTS' FACING QUARTER LIFE CRISIS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to see the differences between male and female students in facing the quarter life crisis phase. This phase is one of the stages experienced by emerging adulthood. Quarter life crisis will be experienced by individuals in their early adulthood who are studying or have finished studying in college and have feelings of worry or anxiety about continuing to live in the future. The sample in this study was 121 students of the Department of Education (IP) FKIP Undana consisting of 35 males (29%) and 86 females (71%). Data collection using proportional random sampling method. Data collection method using Quarter Life Crisis (QLC) scale. Analysis of the data using the Difference Test (T test). The results showed that there was no significant difference between male and female students in the college in facing and overcoming the QLC phase.

Keywords: female, male, college students, quarter life crisis

INTRODUCTION

In today's modern industrial 4.0 and 5.0 society, the journey of the human life span passes through the most complex stages of growth and development. Life span development has been the main focus of psychology for many years starting from the stages of children, adolescents, adults, to the stage of development of the elderly. Each stage of life development has characteristics, tasks and demands that must be met, and brings major interrelated changes in the developmental realm (Papalia, D.E, Old, S.W, Feldman, R.D, 2008).

In early adulthood, Hurlock (1980) is a search stage filled with problems, emotional tension, periods of social isolation, and changes in values and adjustments to life patterns. One of the prominent characteristics of adulthood is that early adulthood is called the troubled period. In the early years of adulthood there are new problems that must be faced by individuals who demand responsibility. Changes that exist at this time the individual experiences many changes, both physical, cognitive, and psychosocio-emotional changes, towards a more mature and wise personality. According to Hurlock (1980) Individuals who are classified as young adults or young adulthood are aged 20-40 years.

Early adulthood full of challenges demands an individual's readiness to find solutions and resilience to face the problems that arise. Self-confidence to control self-functioning, recognition of self-potential, being wise before acting are integral to the self-efficacy that individuals have in the face of challenges in early adulthood (Afnan, A., Fauzia, R., & Tanau, M. U. (2020). It is alleged that individuals with a high level of self-efficacy can reduce the appearance of stress caused by the demands of life.

The challenging, emotionally draining, energy-consuming and life-decisions phase of this period is known as the Quarter Life Crisis (QLC). QLC refers to an individual's concern about facing life in the future regarding relationships, work, social life, dreams and hopes, religion, as well as academic issues (Habibie, A., Syakarofath, N. A., & Anwar, Z. (2019). This emotional crisis can be influenced by family factors (demands from parents), stress academic problems (Afnan, A., et al, 2020), social loneliness, and depression (Lisznyai, S., Vida, K., Németh, M., & Benczúr, Z. (2014).

Quarter life crisis will be experienced by individuals in early adulthood who are or have finished their education in college and have feelings of worry or anxiety to continue living in the future. A person will explore himself more deeply in that phase. The things explored usually include the fields of education, career, and relationships with the opposite sex. Some individuals can successfully find a solution and overcome the crisis experienced. However, some other individuals experience confusion during this time of crisis and need help from others or professionals. Meanwhile, academic problems found in students include difficulty participating in online learning, difficulty completing final projects, and difficulty collecting data as reference material (Rahmania, F. A., & Tasaufi, M. N. F. (2020)).

The variety of problems faced by each individual with different levels, affects the individual's ability to solve them. This is influenced from within the individual as well as the environment around the individual. Sex differences between male and female students also affect emotional and intellectual differences. Women stand out more with their character being more emotional, not aggressive, easily wavering in the face of crises, crying more often, and having difficulty hiding emotions, while men stand out more with their character of unemotional nature, very aggressive, not easily wavering in the face of crises, crying less/less, and can hide emotions (Novtan, R. R., & Putra, Y. Y. (2021). Thus, the existence of differences in individual characteristics emotionally and intellectually based on gender between men and women can be an element that distinguishes the two in the face of a quarter life crisis.

Education Science (IP) is one of the majors at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education at Nusa Cendana University, which consists of 5 (five) Study Programs, namely Elementary School Teacher Education (PGSD), Guidance and Counseling (BK), Early Childhood Education Teacher (PG PAUD), Health and Recreation Physical Education (Penjaskesrek) and Out-of-School Education (PLS). The number of students in the IP department is approximately close to 2000 students. 35% of the number of students are students who are in the final semester and are currently pursuing a thesis or final project. Problems that often arise in students in this final semester are uncertainty about the future after graduating from college, fear of not completing lectures on time, parental demands and high family expectations and other things such as financial problems, early marriage, and others.

This is in accordance with what was revealed by one of the students (KT) of the Guidance and Counseling study program who is in the first semester of X and is at the stage of completing the thesis,

“At this time my concern was if I could not finish my thesis on time. I had a semester off because I was pregnant and married. Parents always ask when my thesis is finished because the cost is no longer there. Meanwhile, I am also still trying to achieve what they expected, plus my mind is divided into thesis and household and arrears of completing unfinished courses”

In addition, a student in the Early Childhood Education Teacher (MA) study program in semester XIII revealed a different problem,

"I have a hard time getting the references needed for my thesis writing. Then I was constrained by a broken laptop, almost all my data was there. I was stressed, I finally didn't continue my writing at all. Right now, I'm trying to get up again to have the spirit of writing by borrowing a friend's laptop"

The quarter-life crisis experienced by a person does not present itself, there are various factors that trigger the onset of a crisis in early adulthood that the individual passes through. Murray, J. L., & Arnett, J. J. (2019), explained that there are 2 factors that affect the quarter life crisis, namely internal factors and external factors.

Internal factors are factors posed by the individual himself, here are the internal factors that affect the quarter life crisis, such as; (a) Identity Exploration. It is the period of individual to explore themselves deeply, desires as well as expectations for the future. Exploration of identity begins with what kind of life will be lived or what they will be like in the future. The focus is on interpersonal relationships, careers, and finding true identity. The breadth of the range and the impact of such exploration not only bring pleasure to the individual, but the consequences caused can create emotional stress such as anxiety, mood disorders, and feelings of fear. This is because in the exploration phase the individual is not only faced with pleasure, there are difficult phases that go through, and if the individual does not prepare well, then, these emotional stresses arise. (b) Instability. The ever-changing development of the times is also one of the causes of problems experienced by individuals. Currently, people in their 20s are those who are busy with various kinds of challenges such as academic challenges, finding a job, anxiety to live independently. It is different to 1970 in general a person who was 21 years old had entered the age of marriage, was busy with welcoming the birth of a child, had completed education, had a permanent job, and so on. The changes that occur continuously due to rapid technology and overtime, as well as the demands that must be met by the individual ultimately require them to live a life that does not correspond to what they planned. (c) Being self-focused. Although in every process of human's life there are others who help or accompany but the individual will eventually make their choice independently, there is a desire to be independent, learn to make decisions, and be responsible for it, to prepare for life in the future. This condition is certainly not an easy thing, there are various difficult decisions that will be faced by individuals such as; appropriate decisions, would have bright future, majoring

decisions, etc. (d) feeling in between. In this phase, there will be a feeling of being between the adolescent and adult phases. When an individual cannot meet the criteria as an adult such as being responsible, able to make decisions, being independent, having good finances, can causes a feeling in the individual that they are not fully mature or they feel that they are still teenager (e) the age of possibilities. In this phase the individual will be faced with a very diverse range of possibilities, be it work, education, life partner, or perspective. The expectations of the individual in this phase are extraordinary, but on the other hand the individual will also be in a position to question these expectations and desires, so that in the end it will cause fear, anxiety, worry about the non-achievement of their hopes and desires.

Meanwhile, the external factors caused QLC, such as; (a) Friends, Romance, And Relationships with Family, (b) work life and career, (c) challenges in academy. In a quarter-life crisis there are aspects that underlie the occurrence of this crisis. According to Robbins & Wilner (2001) in Ameliya, R. P. (2020) there are seven aspects in the quarter life crisis, namely: doubt in making a decision, despair, negative self-assessment, being trapped in difficult situations, anxiety, distress, worrying about interpersonal relationships.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

Based on the problems to be studied, a quantitative research approach is used. This quantitative approach aims to find out the differences between male and female students in facing the quarter life crisis in IP, FKIP, UNDANA.

Population and Sample

Population

The population of this study is last semester students, especially students in the ninth semester of Education Science, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Nusa Cendana University, Kupang. The reason why the author chose the final semester students, especially the ninth semester because the last year students are experiencing psychological pressures, such as loneliness, difficulty to write a thesis, low self-esteem, etc.

Sample

In this study, the sampling technique used was the Proportional Random Sampling technique, which is a technique of random sampling without paying attention to the strata that exist in the population itself. there are 121 students are chosen.

Data Collection Methods

The data collection technique in this study used a QLC questionnaire. In this research questionnaire contains positive and negative statements contained in the Likert scale table.

Validity Test

The validity test used correlation formula of product moment Pearson. From 50 items of QLC questionnaire, 41 items are valid, and 9 items are invalid. The items were declared invalid because r counted $< r$ table $\alpha = 0.05$.

Data Analysis Techniques

The subjects in this study were students of Science Education, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Nusa Cendana University, consisting of students of the PJKR, PLS, PGSD, PGPAUD, and BK study programs who are currently in the ninth semester, totaling 121 people. All the subjects of this study by sex are depicted through the following table

Table 1: The Percentage of Female and Male Students

Sex	amount	Percentage (%)
Male	35	29%
Female	86	71%
Total	121	100%

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the subjects in this study were dominated by female students totaling 86 people with a percentage of 71% and in male subjects totaling 35 people with a percentage of 29%. There was a difference in the number of percentages in subjects due to random sampling without questioning gender. In addition, this is also because sampling is carried out proportionally or balanced, which is 35% of each total population in each study programs.

Based on the results of the distribution of quarter-life crisis instruments to 121 students. Each statement is measured by a score of 1- 4. The highest score for the quarter life crisis variable is 164 and the lowest score is 41. The highest score is obtained from the number of statement items multiplied by the highest score i.e. (41×4) and the lowest score is obtained from the number of items multiplied by the lowest score i.e. (41×1) . Then the range of quarter life crisis variable scores is $164 - 41 = 123$. Thus, the standard unit of deviation is $\sigma = 123/6 = 20.5$ and its theoretical mean is $\mu = 41 \times 3 = 123$. So, an overview of the quarter life crisis in FKIP Undana Education students can be seen through the following table

Table 2: Descriptive Percentage of Students

No	Range Score	Students			Percentage	Category
		M	F	TOTAL		
	$143 \leq X \leq 164$	0	0	0	0%	High
	$103 \leq X \leq 144$	19	48	86	71%	Middle
	$X < 103$	16	38	35	29%	Low
	Jumlah	121orang			100%	

It can be seen that the quarter life crisis experienced by students of FKIP Undana Education is divided into three groups, namely, high with a percentage of 0%, middle with a percentage of

71%, and low with a percentage of 29%. Based on this percentage, it can be concluded that the quarter life crisis experienced by male and female students is classified as middle.

Differential Test

Researchers conducted Differential Tests using the help of SPSS 25 software with the paired sample t-test formula. This formula is a parametric test that can be used on paired data with the aim of seeing if there is a difference between two samples that are paired or related. The following is a table of the results of the Test of Differences in quarter-life crisis variables between males and females.

Table 3: Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Male - Female	3,34286	17,56491	2,96901	-2,69090	9,37661	1,126	34	0,268

Based on the table above, the value of 1.126 with a significance of 0.268 is obtained, which means that $0.286 > 0.05$. Based on the results of the difference test, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between men and women. In other words, the quarter life crisis experienced by men and women has no significant difference.

DISCUSSIONS

The subjects in this study were students totaling 121 people. The subjects in this study were dominated by female students totaling 86 people with a percentage of 71% and in male students totaling 35 people with a percentage of 29%. There was a difference in the number of percentages in subjects due to random sampling without regard to gender. In addition, this is also because sampling is carried out proportionally or balanced, which is 35% of each total population in each study program so that the number of samples depends on the number of populations in the study program itself.

Based on the results of the analysis of quarter life crisis data obtained through 3 categories, namely high with a percentage of 19% with a total of 23 respondents, the middle category with a percentage of 64% with a total of 78 respondents, a low category with a percentage of 17% with a total of 20 respondents. Based on the results of the analysis of research data on the description of the quarter life crisis, it can be concluded that students of FKIP Undana have a picture of the quarter life crisis in the middle category.

QLC is a crisis experienced by individuals as a result of the instability between expectations and reality that occurs in the real world, causing anxiety, fear, worry, indecision, and lack of confidence, difficulty making decisions, and even causing the individual to become desperate. The amount of pressure and expectations from others that are too dominant cause individuals

to be trapped in difficult situations. This is in line with the opinion expressed by Arini, D.P (2021) in her research that, and this quarter century crisis is a situation where there is instability in individuals who enter the real world of life. The instability that occurs causes change and confusion because of the many alternative choices that exist. When individuals cannot determine and find choices, it will cause panic and helplessness.

Quarter Life Crisis is a phase where an emotional crisis occurs in individuals in their 20s, emotional crises that occur in individuals in the quarter life crisis include feelings of helplessness, feeling doubtful or doubtful of one's own abilities, isolation and often fear, anxiety about future failures. (Atwon & Scholtz in Balzarie & Nawangsari, 2019).

Some aspects that are often a problem for individuals who enter the Quarter life Crisis in the book *Mantra Kehidupan Sebuah Refleksi Melewati Fresh Graduate Syndrome* written by Wibowo (2017) that individual is often unsure of the way of life they are living, a sense of doubt that often comes, feeling unsatisfied with what they achieved and what they currently have, unclear about romantic relationships, feeling just a grain of dust in life, often feeling like a failure, feeling often trapped in a life that is not as expected, feeling homesick for past lives or school days, feeling insecure with financial conditions, difficulty in making decisions, often wishing to run away from the reality they are facing, often changing jobs, spouses and places of residence, lack of self-confidence, fear of the future, far from spirituality, self-hatred, not knowing what they want, hard to determine choices and priorities, often comparing their situation with others and socially there is pressure to immediately live well with other people's standards.

Based on research conducted by Sari, M. A. P., & Prastiti, W. D. (2021) on 5 Millennials (born in the 90s-2000s) in Surakarta, consisting of 4 women and 1 man, all of them revealed that the crisis they experienced was anxiety about the future such as a life partner, the desire to make parents happy, work and self-confidence. Of the 5 respondents, 3 of whom are women stated that they do not yet fully have an awareness of their desires and goals in life, and do not know enough about their strengths or potential. While 1 male respondent and 1 female respondent stated that 80% of individuals were able to know themselves and care about developing their potential. However, all respondents realized that to get out of the crisis they faced, they needed to manage their lives better, think positively and try to recognize their potential. This is done in order to develop themselves and have a better life.

The same thing was found in this study, that the negative self-assessment aspect was in the weak category (25%) which was related to low self-confidence and comparing their life with others. This is related to the lack of individual awareness in knowing their personality and their potential so that they tend to feel inferior towards friends who have come out of the QLC phase. In addition, a weak aspect from the calculation results of the QLC instrument is interpersonal relationships (9%), indicating that emerging adulthood students do not have anxiety related to relationships with family, friends, same or different sex.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, it was found that both students, male or female, did not have a striking difference in dealing with the quarter life crisis. The biggest anxiety is the inability to have a positive self-assessment of oneself so that the tendency to have low self-confidence and compare life with others. However, the students did not have any anxiety or crisis in interpersonal relationships either with family or friends.

However, this study still has a weakness, namely the unbalanced percentage of the sample used. The number of male students is smaller than female. And also, the search for each aspect of QLC is not separated between men and women, it is hoped that further researchers will explore other things that are more specific related to QLC.

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